

Deep Learning-based wearable device to prevent fall from height injuries

1st Nicholas Cartocci
Advanced Robotics

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
16163, Genova, Italy
nicholas.cartocci@iit.it

2nd Antonios E. Gkikakis
Advanced Robotics

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
16163, Genova, Italy
antonios.gkikakis@iit.it

3rd Darwin G. Caldwell
Advanced Robotics

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
16163, Genova, Italy
darwin.caldwell@iit.it

4th Jesús Ortiz
Advanced Robotics

Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia
16163, Genova, Italy
jesus.ortiz@iit.it

Abstract—Developing a general-purpose wearable real-time fall-detection system is still a challenging task, especially for healthy and strong subjects, such as industrial workers that work in harsh environments. In this work, we present a hybrid approach for fall detection and prevention, which uses the dynamic model of an inverted pendulum to generate simulations of falls that are then fed into a deep learning framework. The output is a signal to activate a fall mitigation mechanism when the subject is at risk of harm. The advantage of this approach is that abstracted models can be used to efficiently generate training data for thousands of different subjects with different falling initial conditions, something that is practically impossible with real experiments. This approach is suitable for a specific type of fall, where the subjects fall without changing their initial configuration significantly, and it is the first step toward a general-purpose wearable device, with the aim of reducing fall-associated injuries in industrial environments, which can improve the safety of workers.

Index Terms—Fall detection, fall from height, wearable robot, machine learning, deep learning, physical modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), falls take the lives of 684 thousand people each year. In addition to the number of deaths, another 172 million people suffer disability each year due to falls. Over the past two decades, fall-related deaths have increased much faster than any other type of injury. This increase is due to many factors, including the aging population and urbanization patterns [1]. A key aspect of developing fall prevention systems is the detection and/or forecasting of the fall event. Recent developments in the field of embedded sensors and electronics allow the integration of these technologies into wearable devices. However, real-time fall detection is still challenging due to the data quality (in the presence of interference and unstructured environments), the quantity, the heterogeneity of data, and the stringent processing time requirements (the fall must be detected within a narrow time frame). Our work, therefore, takes the critical issues and opportunities highlighted above and involves the study and integration of Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms for the detection and forecasting of falls. Specifically, our approach consists of three parts: (1) detecting

a fall while happening, (2) predicting when the subject might be harmed during the fall in the near future, and (3) activating the prevention mechanism to save the subject. This research aims to find a software solution that can be integrated into a plug-and-play wearable device/robot suitable for different people, regardless of age, gender, and physical structure; it should work efficiently and effectively in most environments to prevent harm to workers as a result of an impact after falling from their feet, or heights. Unlike most previous studies [2]–[4], we focus on developing a wearable for industrial workers. Particularly those who work on construction sites are subject to higher risks; they are forced into heavy and stressful repetitive operations that affect their psychological and physical health more than other categories. Furthermore, most studies ignore the reaction of the subject. For example, a young and healthy subject will not fall the same way as an older person, but, in many cases, may be agile enough to stop the fall by moving quickly or getting a hold of a surrounding object. This introduces false positives that cause the wrong activation of the prevention system and could dissuade users from wearing it. Therefore, detecting a fall is not sufficient for our purpose but activation of the prevention mechanism at the appropriate time is a requirement, which depends on the user’s physical abilities, current mental and health state, and surroundings.

II. METHODOLOGY

The primary goal entails developing a wearable device characterized by durability, untethered operation, ergonomic design, lightweight construction, and unobtrusiveness to motion. Additionally, the sensing technology must have high bandwidth to effectively detect rapid movements while demonstrating resilience in the face of noisy industrial settings and diverse environmental conditions. Accordingly, the initial prototype will integrate Inertial Measurement Units (IMUs) in view of these requirements. Furthermore, in order to achieve the objectives of the study, it is crucial to evaluate and compare the performance of the ML/DL techniques based on this sensor, their training, and the real-time execution. In particular, DL techniques, such as Neural Networks (NNs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), and Recurring Neural Networks (RNNs), are extensively investigated since autonomous feature extraction exploits data heterogeneity better than ML tech-

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niques [2].

In the conduct of this study, a key resource is the public datasets already used for fall detection in the literature, i.e., the SisFall dataset [5], UP-Fall [6] and UMAFall [7]. With these datasets, it is possible to compare the results obtained with each sensor combination and the results obtained from state-of-the-art and proposed ML/DL techniques. However, as noted in [2], most public datasets use few sensors and contain only simulated falls by researchers. Therefore, they do not reflect all types of people, and subjects are aware that they are going to fall, affecting their behavior. These datasets help to understand the dynamics of the fall but not to know its causes. Moreover, analyzing the datasets, we realized that the authors use sensors of limited quality in some of them. Thus, the stored data are polluted by noise and suffer from the problem of sensor drift, especially if the participants perform high-impact activities, such as running or walking fast, before simulating the fall. In addition, although there are public datasets [5]–[7], the number of different subjects and fall scenarios is very limited, and deep learning algorithms need big data to be trained and provide generalized solutions.

Creating a generalized model for all types of falls while taking into account all possible actions and interactions of a human is an extremely difficult task. Hence, we follow a divide-and-conquer approach, with our first sub-problem being cases where users retain their posture throughout the fall (or do not change their configuration significantly). In this type of fall, a human can be approximated as an Inverted Pendulum (IP). This type of assumption has also been used in humanoid robots for fall detection and prevention [8]; however, in our case, we cannot obtain a detailed dynamic model of each human that uses the wearable, and for this reason, we seek a generalized real-time solution with the use of ML/DL approaches. This simplified model, which is computationally cheap, allows the simulation of hundreds of thousands of falls with different initial conditions and physical characteristics (height, inertia, etc.) within a few hours, in contrast, to computationally expensive simulations of realistic humanoid models that might require significantly more time to complete.

For practical purposes, one or a set of IMUs that output orientation data can be attached to a user. In the dataset of [5], the authors have chosen to place an IMU on the user's waist, and [6] on the left wrist, at the right pocket of the user's pants, in the middle of the waist, and under the neck. The number and placement of the IMUs are still under investigation, which will be the result of real experiments. Finally, the complete framework is currently being integrated into a real-time system.

III. FALL DETECTION AND FORECASTING

Our Fall Prevention system is developed in two cascade parts: Fall Detection and Fall Forecasting. The first part is used to detect whether the person is falling or performing a normal (non-hazardous) activity; while the second part estimates the evolution of the fall and the time of impact to the ground. The proposed approach was presented in more detail in [9].

A. Fall Detection

A deep recurrent neural network (RNN) was chosen for data-based fall detection, where the data used to train the neural network are obtained from the SisFall dataset [5] labeled in [10]. The network has multiple inputs, consisting of both the inherent characteristics of the subjects and a multivariate time series. The output is the probability of falling $\mathcal{P}(\text{falling})$, and if $\mathcal{P}(\text{falling}) > 0.5$, the subject is assumed to be falling.

B. Fall Forecasting

Fall forecasting refers to the forecasting of the future state of a subject who is falling, assuming that the subject will continue to fall. Again, a deep learning approach is studied that extrapolates the subject's orientation in the future and identifies when the subject will be at risk of harm. However, unlike the data-driven fall detection algorithm, the dataset used to train and validate the NN is derived from the inverted pendulum model. The forecasting time should be longer than the activation time of the fall mitigation system. Considering, for example, an airbag mechanism with an activation time of 80-100 ms, a forecasting time of 200 ms is assumed to be sufficient to apply an appropriate mitigation policy.

IV. RESULTS

The Fall Prevention system was evaluated on the SisFall dataset, and the mitigation system was activated in 100% of the sequences with falls, *Accuracy* = 100%, and erroneously in only 0.6% of the ADL sequences, *Accuracy* = 99.4%.

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